

Democratic advocacy: Representation of social workers in the cantonal and national parliaments of Switzerland

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Social work and social policy-making are closely intertwined (e.g. Leiber et al., 2023; Dischler & Kulke, 2021). The Swiss professional organization of social work, AvenirSocial (2010), defines the initiation of social policy interventions as a core task of social work. In its code of ethics, AvenirSocial even calls on social workers to use their civic resources in their free time to fight for a democratic and socially just society, e.g., by voting or demonstrating. There are various ways in which social workers can respond to this call and be proactive in shaping policy, including holding elected political office (Amann & Kindler, 2021, 2022).

An ideal place to examine this strategy of policy engagement is Switzerland, with its unique federal and direct democratic political institutions (Kehl, 2023; Kindler, 2023; Linder & Mueller, 2021; Vatter, 2018). In this country, Swiss citizens – and thus a majority of Swiss social workers – have the right to run for political office at the local, cantonal, and national levels.

At the local level, Switzerland consists of 2136 municipalities (BFS, 2023a). As of January 2023, 461 of them have a parliament, varying in size between 9 and 124 seats (Strebel, 2023). In other municipalities, the assembly of all citizens constitute the legislative body. At the cantonal level, each canton has its own parliament, which varies in size from 50 to 180 seats. Taken together, all cantonal parliaments consist of 2594 elected members. Unlike the local and cantonal levels, the national parliament consists of two chambers. The Council of States, which represents the cantons, has 46 seats. The National Council, which represents the people, has 200 seats.

In accordance with the militia system – a typically Swiss political institution based on the “idea of volunteering one’s time to perform political and social tasks communities need” (Ladner, 2019, p. 13) – all the members of the local, cantonal, and national parliaments are active as politicians in addition to their main occupation in various professional fields. This research note examines the number and proportion of social workers who hold elected office as members of cantonal and national parliaments.

The following figures are based on the cantonal state calendars (e.g., Canton Zug, 2023), the official websites of the cantonal parliaments (e.g., Canton Zurich, 2023), and the official website of the national parliament (The Swiss Parliament, n.d.). All job titles are based on self-reporting by members of the parliaments (MPs) in the above-mentioned documents. See Kindler (2024) for the complete data set.

As can be seen in **Table 1**, the canton of Lucerne has the highest number of social workers currently serving in the cantonal parliament. The proportion of social workers is also high in the cantons of Schaffhausen, Basel-Stadt or St.Gallen. **Table 2** shows the numbers and proportions of social workers holding elected political office in the national parliament.

Table 1. Number and proportion of social workers holding elected political office in the cantonal parliaments in Switzerland (as of January 1st, 2024)
(Source: own compilation)

Canton	Total seats	Social workers (n)	Social workers (%)
AG	140	2	1.4%
AI	50	0	0.0%
AR	65	2	3.1%
BE	160	4	2.5%
BL	90	1	1.1%
BS	100	5	5.0%
FR	110	1	0.9%
GE	100	2	2.0%
GL	60	0	0.0%
GR	120	4	3.3%
JU	60	2	3.3%
LU	120	9	7.5%
NE	100	3	3.0%
NW	60	0	0.0%
OW	55	0	0.0%
SG	120	5	4.2%
SH	60	4	6.7%
SO	100	2	2.0%
SZ	100	0	0.0%
TG	130	3	2.3%
TI	90	0	0.0%
UR	64	1	1.6%
VD	150	5	3.3%
VS	130	3	2.3%
ZG	80	2	2.5%
ZH	180	5	2.8%

Table 2. Number and proportion of social workers holding elected political office in the national parliament of Switzerland (as of January 1st, 2024)
(Source: own compilation)

Chamber	Total seats	Social workers (n)	Social workers (%)
Nationalrat	200	3	1.5%
Ständerat	46	2	4.3%

As shown in **Figure 1**, the professional backgrounds in the cantonal parliaments that are most frequently mentioned in the cantonal state calendars and official parliamentary websites as of January 1st, 2024 are farmer (9.3%), lawyer (8.2%), teacher (8.2%), and economist (8.1%). Among the 2,594 elected cantonal MPs, there are 65 social workers (2.5%). To learn more about the names and current positions of these 65 social workers, see Kindler (2024).

The Swiss Federal Statistical Office (BFS, 2023b) estimates a working population of 4.4 million in 2021, of which 50,000 are identified as social workers, 83,600 are identified as farmers, etc. Based on this representative survey, which includes data on all occupations in Switzerland, Figure 1 allows us to compare the actual incidence of selected occupations (gray bars) with their share in the cantonal parliaments in Switzerland (black bars). This comparison shows that most of the selected occupations are overrepresented in the cantonal parliaments. This is particularly true for lawyers and farmers, both of which are strongly overrepresented, but also for social workers, who are overrepresented in the cantonal parliaments relative to their incidence in the total working population.

Figure 1. Share of selected professionals in the cantonal parliaments of Switzerland (as of January 1st, 2024) (Sources: BFS, 2023b; own compilation)

As shown in **Figure 2**, the professional backgrounds of the 246 members of the national parliament in Switzerland, as mentioned on the official website of the parliament as of January 1st, 2024, are lawyer (21.1%), economist (8.9%), and farmer (7.3%). The national parliament is composed of the National Council (200 seats) and the Council of the States (46 seats) and includes a total of five social workers. The three social work members of the National Council are Barbara Gysi, Katharina Prelicz-Huber, and Manuela Weichelt. The two social work members of the Council of the States are Barbara Graf and Simon Stocker.

As in Figure 1, **Figure 2** allows us to compare the actual incidence of selected professions (gray bars) with their share in the Swiss national parliament (black bars), based on the representative statistics on professions from the Swiss Federal Statistical Office (BFS, 2023b) and this own compilation. At the national level, lawyers are even more overrepresented than at the cantonal level: While 21.1% of the members of the national parliament are lawyers, only 0.8% of the total working population is employed in this field. At the national level, 2.0% of the MPs are social workers.

Figure 2. Share of selected professionals in the national parliament of Switzerland (as of January 1st, 2024) (Sources: BFS, 2023b; own compilation)

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